

AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF COPPER WITH SALICYLAMIDOXIME

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A rapid method for the determination of copper(II) by amperometric titration with salicylamidoxime has been developed by which 0.4 to 8 mg. of copper (conc. ca. 0.7–3.2 *M*) can be determined with accuracy in an acetate buffer medium of *pH* ca. 4.2, using a simple manual apparatus with a microammeter (0–50 μ A) of a large scale for measuring the current. Direct titration of copper is possible in presence of lead, cadmium, zinc, manganese, cobalt and nickel; while in the presence of silver, antimony and bismuth excess of potassium chloride is to be added prior to the addition of the buffer in order to precipitate these metals, and then copper is titrated in the supernatant liquid.

In earlier communications [Bandyopadhyay (Banerjea) and Rây, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 21, 65; Bandyopadhyay (Banerjea), *ibid.*, p. 269, 270; Banerjea, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 159, 123] the reactions of salicylamidoxime with metallic ions and some of their analytical applications have been described. The quantitative precipitation of copper(II) by this reagent from an acetate buffer medium (*pH*, ca. 4.2) has now been made use of in the amperometric determination of this metal at a potential of $-0.2V$ vs. S. C. E., using a dropping mercury electrode, where the diffusion current due to the reaction $Cu(II) \rightarrow Cu(O)$ is fully developed, whereas the reagent does not undergo any change anywhere in the vicinity of this potential. Small amounts of copper (0.4 to 8.0 mg.) at very low concentrations (0.7 to 3.2 *mM*) can be determined with accuracy, using a simple manual set-up. The presence of a little gelatin (0.01%) as a maximum suppressor is necessary in the titrating solution. The method works well even in the presence of metals like lead, cadmium, zinc, manganese, cobalt and nickel, and excess of alkali metal salts (chloride, nitrate or sulphate) in solution. In the presence of silver, antimony and bismuth, it is necessary to add an excess of potassium chloride, before adding the buffer, in order to precipitate these metals and then titrate copper in the supernatant liquid.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Cambridge Pen-recording polarograph was used for recording the polarograms, while the amperometric titrations were carried out in a cylindrical glass cell, connected to an external saturated calomel electrode through an agar—KCl bridge, using a manual circuit of the type described by Meites ("Polarographic Techniques", p. 8, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, 1955) having a microammeter (0–50 μ A; Model 726 of M/s. Triplett Electrical Instrument Co., U S. A.) for measuring the current. A dropping mercury electrode of drop time (ca. 3 secs.) was used as the indicator electrode.

Salicylamidoxime.—A pure sample of the substance was prepared as described earlier (Bandyopadhyay and Rây, *loc. cit.*). A freshly prepared aqueous solution of this was used for the titrations.

Copper(II) solution.—A stock solution of copper nitrate was prepared from accurately weighed metallic copper (Electrolytic, E. Merck) and dilute nitric acid.

Acetate buffer.—Anhydrous sodium acetate (16.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (25.0 c.c.) were dissolved in water and made up to one litre.

All other chemicals used were of reagent quality. Gelatin used was of pure quality (E. Merck, Germany)

Titration Procedure.—The copper(II) solution was neutralised (pH 6-7) with dilute alkali (KOH) and to it 30 c.c. of the acetate buffer was added for every 100 c.c. of the final volume, as also sufficient gelatin. This was diluted to a requisite volume, an aliquot of which was transferred to the titration cell and deaerated with purified nitrogen and then titrated, at $-0.2V$ vs. S. C. E., using the dropping mercury indicator electrode, with an aqueous solution of salicylamidoxime of a suitable concentration (at least 10 times the molar concentration of copper in the solution under titration), recording the current after each successive addition of small increments of the reagent. The end-point was obtained graphically (cf. Meites, *loc. cit.*, p. 195) making allowance for the volume change during the titration. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Amperometric determination of different amounts of copper.

Supporting electrolyte :- sodium acetate (0.06M)-acetic acid buffer (pH, 4.2) containing 0.01% gelatin. Applied potential: $-0.2 V$ vs S. C. E. Drop time = ca. 3 secs. Temp. = 28-30° (room temp.).

Volume of soln. (c.c.)	...	40	40	40	20	20	10
Cu present (mg.)	...	8.13	5.60	4.06	2.44	0.81	0.42
Cu found (mg.)	...	8.19	5.60	4.06	2.42	0.82	0.43
Error (mg.)	..	0.06	0.00	0.00	-0.02	0.01	0.01

In the presence of other metal ions a similar procedure was used and some such determinations are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Estimation of copper in presence of other substances.

(Medium and conditions same as for Table I).

Total substances present in 50 c.c. of which 40 c.c. was titrated.

No.	Substances present.	Copper.			No.	Substances present.	Copper		
		Present.	Found.	Error.			Present.	Found.	Error.
1.	KCl, 500 mg.	6.48 mg.	6.51 mg.	0.03 mg.	7.	Mn, 100 mg.	6.48 mg.	6.44 mg.	-0.04 mg.
2.	KNO ₃ , 500	6.48	6.48	0.00	8.	Co, 100	6.48	6.52	0.04
3.	K ₂ SO ₄ , 500	6.48	6.48	0.00	9.	Ni, 100	6.35	6.30	-0.05
4.	Pb, 100	6.48	6.48	0.00	10.	Ag, 100	6.48	6.44	-0.04
5.	Cd, 100	6.35	6.32	-0.03	11.	Sb, 100	6.48	6.48	0.00
6.	Zn, 100	6.35	6.36	0.01	12.	Bi, 100	6.48	6.55	0.07

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